

DEVELOPMENT OF TESTING USING NON-DESTRUCTIVE TESTING METHODS

A.A. Akbarov¹, Sh.A. Sulaymanov², A.K. Sativaldiev³

Master's student, Andijan Mechanical Engineering Institute¹

PhD., Associate Professor, Andijan Mechanical Engineering Institute²

PhD., Associate Professor, Andijan Mechanical Engineering Institute³

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14834518>

Abstract. *The principle of the ultrasonic testing method is based on the fact that solid materials are good conductors of sound waves. As a result, the waves are reflected not only from boundary surfaces but also from internal defects (cracks, various inclusions, etc.). The effect of interaction between sound waves and the material increases as the wavelength decreases (and, correspondingly, the frequency of oscillations increases).*

Keywords: *ultrasound, sound waves, non-destructive testing, testing, development, defects, impulse.*

INTRODUCTION. Non-destructive testing (NDT) methods are an essential tool for diagnosing and controlling the quality of materials and structures without damaging them. These methods are widely used in various industries, including aviation, automotive, energy, and construction. The development of tests using NDT requires a detailed approach, including the selection of testing methods, equipment preparation, and the analysis and interpretation of the obtained data.

The aim of this article is to consider the process of developing tests using NDT methods, as well as the practical application and analysis of the results obtained. [1-3]

MATERIALS AND METHODS. NDT methods can be classified into several types depending on their operating principles. The main methods include:

- Ultrasonic Testing (UT)– used to detect defects in materials and measure their thickness.
- X-ray and Gamma-ray Testing– helps identify internal defects through radiation.
- Magnetic Testing – applied to materials with magnetic properties, used to detect surface and subsurface defects.
- Capillary Testing– used to detect cracks and other defects on the surface of materials using dyes.

- Visual Inspection– the simplest method for assessing the condition of a material's surface.

RESULTS

The process of developing NDT tests can be divided into several stages:

1. Defining the goals and tasks of the inspection

At this stage, it is essential to precisely formulate which defects or characteristics of the material or structure need to be identified, as well as which NDT methods are most effective for the task.

2. Selection of the NDT method*

Depending on the type of material, the expected depth and nature of the defects, the most suitable NDT method is chosen.

3. Development of the testing procedure

A clear and detailed procedure is developed, which includes a description of all testing stages: preparation of samples, equipment setup, performing the test, and methods for processing results.

4. Testing and data processing

Tests are performed using the selected method, data is collected, and analyzed to detect defects.

5. Evaluation of results and documentation

A report is prepared based on the test results, which includes descriptions of the detected defects, their location, size, and recommendations for further action.

Example of Applying UT

To illustrate, an example of using ultrasonic testing for measuring the thickness of metal in a structure is provided.

Table 1. Results of Ultrasonic Testing for Metal Thickness

Sample	Initial Thickness	Thickness After Testing (mm)	Deviation (mm)
1	10	9.8	-0.2
2	8	8.1	+0.1
3	15	14.7	-0.3
4	20	19.8	-0.2

Ultrasonic Flaw Detector -Before moving on to further control tasks and their solutions, it is necessary to briefly familiarize oneself with the principles of operation of ultrasonic equipment. For example, a simplified algorithm for an analog flaw detector is selected. Modern digital technology works differently, but the principle of transmitting and receiving ultrasonic oscillations remains the same. Based on the previously mentioned locations of discontinuities, short sound pulses must be transmitted into the controlled object to measure the time it takes for the pulse to travel from the transducer to the reflecting surface and back. [4-6]

This is only possible when the start and end times are clearly defined. If the speed of sound in the controlled object is known, simple calculations can determine the distance to the reflecting surface and, thus, the precise location of the discontinuity in the controlled object, as shown in Figure 1

Figure 1. Principle of Measuring Time and Pulse Path

Sound reflections in the audible range are called echoes. Thus, the name of the method used in most material inspections using ultrasound – the Pulse Echo Method, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Block Diagram of the Pulse Echo Method

Time measurement starts with an electrical impulse – an excitation pulse. This is a very short electrical discharge that generates a sound pulse in the transducer's piezoelement. The sound pulse passes through the material and, when reflected from a discontinuity or the opposite surface of the material, returns to the transducer. The received oscillations are converted into an electrical pulse, stopping the time measurement. The distance to the reflecting surface can then be calculated using the following formula:

$$S = \frac{ct}{2}$$

where:

S = path of the sound pulse (mm)

c = speed of sound in the material (km/s)

t = time for the pulse to travel (s)

Now, if the travel time and amplitude of the pulse are displayed graphically, a simplified model of a universal ultrasonic flaw detector is obtained. [7-10] To evaluate the parameters of visual echo signals on the screen, a grid is placed on it. The adjustable scale with horizontal ticks is called the display scale, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Display Scale

Using the scale, the operator can measure the parameters of the reflected signal on the screen. As mentioned earlier, the electrical pulse excites the sound pulse in the transducer.

DISCUSSION

After performing ultrasonic testing, it can be observed that deviations from the nominal thickness of the materials do not exceed the permissible limits, indicating the good condition of the tested samples. Thus, the UT method effectively controls thickness and identifies potential defects in materials.

CONCLUSIONS

The development of testing using non-destructive testing methods requires a comprehensive approach, including the selection of the optimal method, the preparation of a detailed procedure, and thorough processing of the obtained data. The application of NDT methods significantly improves the safety and reliability of structures, while reducing risks associated with the use of defective materials.

In conclusion, it can be noted that non-destructive testing is a vital tool for ensuring the quality and durability of materials, and its application continues to evolve across various industries.

REFERENCES

1. Kamilova O, Akbarov A, Sativaldiev A.K. Kapilyarlarni buzilmaydigan sinov va diaqnozini qo'llash// XXI Asr Ilm-Fan ishlab chiqarishda Metrologiya Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari to'plami 18 may 2023 y. Andijon.
 2. Sativaldiyev A.A., Kasimova D.A., Akbarov.A., Qutbiddinov N. X, Shermamatov Sh.N Ishlab chiqarishda sifat nazorati usullari// Xalqaro miqiyosdagi ilmiy va ilmiy-texnik anjuman to'plami.309 bet 18-19- sentabr, 2023-yil, Andijon.
 3. ГОСТ 18442-80* «Контроль неразрушающий. Капиллярные требования»
 4. РД-13-06-2006 «Методические рекомендации о порядке проведения капиллярного контроля технических устройств и сооружений, применяемых и эксплуатируемых на опасных производственных объектах»
 5. Белокур И. П., Коваленко В. А. Дефектоскопия материалов и изделий. К.: Техника, 1989
 6. ГОСТ — 18442 — 80. Контроль неразрушающий. Капиллярные методы контроля
 7. Ермолов И. Н., Останин Ю. Я. Методы и средства неразрушающего контроля качества. М.: Высшая школа, 1988.
 8. Прохоренко П. П., Мигун Н. П. Введение в капиллярную дефектоскопию. / Под ред. А. С. Боровикова. - Мн.: Наука и техника, 1988
 9. Хамдамов Б. Р., Фаттаев М. А. Практика применения метода СПС для анализа процесса производства велюрного материала //Экономика и социум. – 2022. – №. 5-1 (96). – С. 738-742.
- Pribory dlja nerazrushajushhego kontrolja materialov i izdelij. Spravochnik [Tekst] / Pod red. V.V. Kljueva. – М.: Mashinostroenie, 1986. – 357 s.